

Table 4. Reviewed studies

References	Field background	Main theories and methodologies that guide the paper	Walkable factors (efficiency and comfort, pleasantness, safety, attractiveness)	Type of data: O; EJ; HS	Data and covariables	Sample Social group profile Scale	Assessment method (Aggregation and Spatialization)	Validation
Bader et al. (2013)	Urban planning and Public health	Influence of urban form on people behaviour	Attractiveness: number and type of land uses; Efficiency and comfort: sidewalk width; street design; Safety and security: mix of use; transparency and permeability of built environment; geometry of crossings and facilities for pedestrians at crossings; Pleasantness: aesthetic of place; architectural and landscape design	O; EJ	Audit on line	US metropolitan areas; census tract level	Definition of a CANVAS audit on line tool and reliability of the method	RB
Beiler and Phillips (2015)	Urban planning and public health	Influence of urban form on health, social capital	Attractiveness: mix of use; Efficiency and comfort: cost; sidewalk width; connectivity; continuity; barriers; design of the street; slope; pavement conditions; Safety and security: mix of use; lighting; car traffic volume, design speed of the route; crossing facilities; Pleasantness: aesthetic of place; shelter and shade; sedibility; transparency and permeability	O	GIS data and manual field data collection	Union County four type of paths; street level	Development of a composite index used to rank pathways based on the need for pedestrian improvement. PCI draws on existing federal design guidance and uses GIS and AHP to collect data and define factor weights. The corridor under analysis can include pathway segments and intersections	EX
Bias et al. (2010)	Urban planning and public health	Relation between physical environment and physical activity	Attractiveness: mix of use; Efficiency and comfort: costs, hilliness, street connectivity, Pleasantness: aesthetics; Safety and security: speed of vehicular traffic, availability of sidewalks and crosswalks; presence of people	EJ	Telephone survey	Morgantown and Cabell County, West Virginia 40-65 years old residents;	Assessment of the reliability of a neighbourhood walkability survey instrument to be used by decision makers as an indicator of the physical activity friendliness of a community	SP; RB
Blečić et al. (2015)	Urban and transport planning	Operational measure of urban walkability	Efficiency and comfort: cost distance and slope, street type, bicycle track, footway width and maintenance, shelter and shade, benches; Attractiveness: presence; typology and intensity of activities; building density; Safety and Security: street lighting, on street parking, integration of the street with the surrounding; Pleasantness: scenery; environmental/architectural attractiveness;	O	OSM dataset; built environment data collected with on field audit and computer aided methods	City of Alghero, Italy, street segment level and points of urban fabric	Development of <i>Walkability Explorer</i> an algorithm which processes spatial data and run multicriteria evaluation model to assign walkability scores to points in urban space	-
Boulangé et al. (2018)	Urban and transport Planning	Influence of urban form on walking	Efficiency and comfort: street connectivity; intersection density; distance to closest public transport stop/train station/supermarket; land use mix, dwelling density; Attractiveness: local living destinations; housing diversity	O; EJ	Travel survey and participatory workshop Official GIS, layers, census	Broadmeadows suburb, Melbourne, neighbourhood level	Development of a "Walkability" focused PSS tool able to model and evaluate the impacts of planning decisions on transport-walking and community health outcomes	SP
Buck et al. (2011)	Public health	Influence of urban form on physical activity for children	Efficiency and comfort: intersections density, urban form, sidewalk and transit station presence; Attractiveness: presence of public facilities	O	GIS data, municipal geospatial information system; demos; economic data	Delmenhorst Germany; 596 Children (2-10 years old); block level	<i>Moveability index</i> . Kernel density method with GIS and "container approach" and regression analyses	-
Carr, Dunsiger, Marcus (2011)	Urban planning	Operational measure of urban walkability	Attractiveness: presence and density of activities; Efficiency and comfort: street connectivity, street density, average block length;	O	Census; GIS dataset (Tiger); street network Internet-based reference service database	296 participants, Rhode Island, USA, block level	Walk score method. The score (0–100) calculation is based on the walking distance to the closest amenity ranged in 13 categories equally weighted	EX
Cerin et al. (2006)	Transportation planning and public health	Relationship between urban form and walkability and cyclability for recreation	Efficiency and comfort: shelters and shade; cost; design of the street; design of the street (connectivity), signalization; Pleasantness: scenery; architectural and urban design; cleanliness/pollution; Safety and security: separation features; lighting; volume/crowding if cars in the street;	O; EJ	Neighbourhood surveys and GIS database; socioeconomic status	King County; 16 neighbourhoods 1286 adults; census block	Confirmatory factor analysis to define an abbreviated version of NEWS	RB

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			design of the street; crime/policy presence; urban texture; Attractiveness: presence, density; typology; mix of activities and opportunities;					
Cervero and Duncan (2003)	Urban planning and public health	Influence of urban form on physical activity (walking and bicycling)	Efficiency and comfort: cost distance and slope; street connectivity; block size; walking and cycling facilities; Attractiveness: presence; typology density and intensity of activities; Safety and Security: low income %, street lighting/darkness	<i>O</i>	Census, travel survey, geodatabase and GIS data	San Francisco Bay area, households; block scale	Discrete choice logit modelling to estimate probability of walking and cycling; factor analysis and statistical tests to determine the significance of the various effects	RB
Cervero and Kockelman (1997)	Urban planning	Relationship between built environment and travel demand	Efficiency and comfort: block length, street patterns, proportion of intersections, street connectivity, sidewalk width, slope, street trees; Safety and security: pedestrian and cycling provisions, distance between overhead street lights, signalized intersections, overhead street lights; Attractiveness: population and employment density, commercial intensity, land use mix	<i>O;EJ</i>	Travel data, census, land use data field survey	50 neighbourhood s in the San Francisco Bay Area; census tracts level	statistical models used to predict personal vehicle miles of travel; factor analysis to gauge the relative influence of built environment dimensions on travel demand	RB
Clifton et al. (2007)	Urban planning	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: design of the street; pavement type and conditions; obstructions; continuity of the route; connectivity; cost; off parking facilities; signalization, information availability and signage; Pleasantness: architectural and urban design, cleanliness/pollution; bicycle lanes, urban texture, shelters and shade; Safety and security: lighting; separation features; pavement type and conditions; design speed of the route; on street parking facilities; Attractiveness: presence, number of activities, typology	<i>O</i>	Audit data	College Park and Montgomery County; 3635 segments of a pedestrian network or pathways; street level	Reliability testing of the method and development of a Pedestrian Environmental Data Scan (PEDS)	-
Colclough (2009)	Urban and transport planning	Relationship between physical environment and pedestrian accessibility	Efficiency and comfort: cost, distance, path gradient, block size intersections, street connectivity; Attractiveness: dwelling, density, percentage	<i>O;EJ</i>	OS Integrated Transport Network (ITN), GIS datasets by official sources, digital height data, field audit, survey	West Northamptonshire (UK); 2km catchment area level	GIS-based model to assess pedestrian accessibility based on the relationship between walk speed, gradient and the demographic type of the walker	EX; SP
Emery et al. (2003)	Public health	Influence of urban form on physical activity	Efficiency and comfort: continuity of the route; Safety and Security: Volume of cars on the street; design of the street; pavement conditions; design speed of the route; separation features; lighting	<i>O</i>	Audit and survey data	the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill; 31 urban and rural road segments identified within 10 miles of the campus; street level	Definition of a walking suitability score and a bicycling suitability score and calculation of the intercoder reliability correlation	EX
Ewing and Cervero (2010)	Urban and transportation planning	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: cost and distance to destinations (stores, transit stop, etc.) intersection/street density; Attractiveness: population and job density jobs-housing balance land use mix (entropy index)	<i>O</i>	Data from individual primary studies	-	Meta-analysis and “effect size” computation to esteem the magnitude of the relationships between the built environment and walking	RB
Ewing and Handy (2009)	Urban planning	Relationship between urban form and walkability	Efficiency and comfort: directness of route; sedibility; Pleasantness: volume/crowding of pedestrians on the street; architectural and urban design; noise level; scenery; landscape design; urban texture; Security: activities' atmosphere; Attractiveness: presence, density of active uses; typology indoor/outdoor	<i>O</i>	Survey data	New York; 48 video-clips in commercial streets; street level	Definition with a panel of experts of the urban design qualities that affect the individual perception of the street. Definition of an operative set of objective measures	EX

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Forsyth et al. (2008)	Urban and transportation planning	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour	Efficiency and Comfort: street pattern (road and block length, intersection density,...), pedestrian-oriented infrastructure (sidewalk length, street trees, traffic calming measures, transit stop density, ..); Attractiveness: amenities and mixed use density, entropy index	<i>O; EJ</i>	GIS datasets; survey, seven day travel diary accelerometer, computer mapping and survey	715 participants in the Twin Cities, Minnesota; street and neighbourhood level	Pairwise correlation between objective measures of built environment with self-reported physical activity behaviours	-
Frank et al. (2006); (2010)	Urban planning	Influence of urban form on physical activity	Efficiency and comfort: cost; easy of walk; design of the street (connectivity); cost (frequency of walking); Attractiveness: presence, density of active uses; mix and typology of activities	<i>O</i>	NQoL data; statistical data; survey; demos,	City of Baltimore; adults; Block level	Linear regression to evaluate relations between walkability and health and walkability and emissions. Definition of a walkability index (<i>Neighbourhood quality of life study</i>)	RB
Ghani, Shah and Mokhtar, 2013	Urban and transportation planning	Influence of urban form on travel behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: design of the street (sidewalk presence and continuity), distance, Safety and security: pavement; lighting; separation; signals; traffic calming Attractiveness: presence and proximity of active land uses	<i>O</i>	Field survey on a set of roads of different hierarchy	Taman Bukit Indah, Johor Bahru, Malaysia; neighbourhood and street level	Development of a pedestrian index (P-Index) which incorporates selected indicators according to road hierarchy to be used to evaluate pedestrian facilities using 5 star rating formats. The rating scores are next incorporated into Google Maps to enable the public to visualise	
Giles-Corti et al. (2014)	Urban and transportation planning	Influence of urban form on travel behaviour	Efficiency: street connectivity, Attractiveness: residential or dwelling density and land use mix.	<i>O</i>	Australian state government datasets: cadastre, dwellings, street networks, census	North West Region of Melbourne, Australia; neighbourhood level, walkable service area level (15 min)	Development of an automated geospatial tool, based on open-source datasets capable of computing walkability indices at user-specified scales (AURIN)	EX
Glazier et al. (2013)	Public health	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: cost; street connectivity; Attractiveness: presence, density and mix land use; Security: urban texture;	<i>O</i>	Statistical data Demos	City of Toronto, 248 million people census tracts and block level	Factor analysis to identify components of the built environment as measures of walkability; components analysis used to construct a walkability index	RB
Hajna et al. (2013)	Public health	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: design of the street (connectivity; sidewalk presence); continuity of the route; cost; Safety and security: pavement; lighting; feel safe; Pleasantness: urban texture; Attractiveness: presence, density of active uses	<i>O; EJ</i>	Statistical data; Audit data	Montreal; adults with diabetes; street level	Index of walkability (<i>Pedestrian environment data scan</i>) and relations with the perceptions of walkability	EX
Handy and Tal (2011)	Integrated land use and transport planning	Relationship between urban form and pedestrian connectivity and accessibility	Efficiency and comfort: distance, directness, connectivity; Attractiveness: density and variety of amenities	<i>O</i>	GIS datasets, pedestrian network, demos	City of Davis, USA suburban areas; neighbourhood and street level	Analysis of pedestrian accessibility and connectivity and comparison between neighbourhoods	EX; RB
Iacono et al. (2010)	Urban and transportation planning	Relationship between physical environment and non motorized travel (walking and cycling) behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: impedance distance and time, pedestrian and bicycling facilities; Attractiveness: presence, number, type, dimension of land-use	<i>O; EJ</i>	Household travel survey data; Establishment-level data; parcel-level land use data	1600 block groups in South Minneapolis; block level	Development of an accessibility measure for non-motorized modes (walking and cycling) for different types of destinations. Travel survey data used for estimating the impedance function	RB
Keyvanfar et al. 2018	Integrated land use and transport planning	Relationship between physical environment and pedestrian behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: width of walking zones, sidewalks networking; street furniture, trees, shelters, street lighting, type of sidewalk pavement, steepness, obstacles/nuisance; Safety and security: bike lanes, on-street parking, mid-block crossings, traffic signals, signage, traffic calming devices, medians, lighting, street surveillance, street-facing entrances, street-level façade transparency; Pleasantness: enclosure, buffer zone; Attractiveness: land use mix, diversity of buildings	<i>EJ</i>	self-report questionnaire to capture pedestrian's DTM for walking towards 3 shopping centres.	Taman University neighbourhood, Skudai city, Malaysia; path and neighbourhood level	Development of the <i>Path Walkability Assessment (PWA) Index Model</i> based on the pedestrian's decision tree model in determining the "well-designed" walking routes, intended as streets that incorporate the walkability design codes and standards that facilitate and fulfil pedestrian's preferences and needs.	SP

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Koohsari et al. (2013)	Public health	Relationship between urban form and walkability; Influence of urban form on physical activity	Efficiency and comfort: shelters and shade; cost; design of the street; design of the street (connectivity), signalization; Pleasantness: scenery; architectural and urban design; cleanliness/pollution; Safety and security: separation features; lighting; volume/crowding if cars in the street; design of the street; crime/policy presence; Attractiveness: presence and number of active services and urban opportunities; presence, density, typology of services	<i>O; EJ</i>	Neighbourhood surveys (questionnaires); GIS databases; demos	Melbourne; 330 households 990	Analysis of urban features related to people's behaviour (differentiated by individual characteristics) in different urban settings by streets configuration types: (a)the core area of the city; (b)a grid pattern; (c)a mixture of regularity and irregularity; (d) street typically curved or rectangular	RB
Krizek (2003)	Urban planning	Relationship between physical environment and neighbourhood accessibility	Efficiency and comfort: block size intersection density, street connectivity; Attractiveness: presence and density housing residents and employees, land use mix	<i>O</i>	Census block-level data, GIS dataset (Tiger)	Central Puget Sound metropolitan area, Washington; 150-meter grid cells level	Development of a Neighbourhood Accessibility Index which combines together into a single factor (NA score) detailed measures of density, land use mix, and street patterns	EX
Lee and Moudon (2006)	Urban planning	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour.	Efficiency and comfort: cost, route directness; Attractiveness: number of services and urban opportunities; presence and density of active uses; type of services and activities; mix of activities	<i>O</i>	Survey data, GIS data, demos	Seattle and suburban area; 608 adult; census block level	Definition of the Behavioural Model of Environment to select the environmental variables. The BME consists of three spatial constructs associated with walking behaviour: the 'origin and destination' of trips, the 'area' characteristics around the origin and destination, and the characteristics of the 'route' connecting the origin and destination	RB
Leslie et al. (2007)	Urban planning and public health	Influence of urban form on physical activity	Efficiency and comfort: connectivity Attractiveness: density Safety and security: mixed use;	<i>O</i>	Dwelling data, tax valuation and cadastral (parcel) data, PLACE data Census	Adelaide, Australia; census tract level	Definition of a Walkability index and maps of walking conduciveness	RB
Lwin and Murayama (2011)	Urban planning	Relation between urban environment and walkability; influence of urban form on physical activity	Efficiency and comfort: cost and distance; Pleasantness: scenery; Attractiveness: number of activities; quality and building footprint	<i>O</i>	Fine scale GIS data	Tsukuba, Japan; street level	Greenness score of urban locations based on "cumulative opportunity" measures	-
Moura et al. (2017)	Urban and transportation planning	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour of different groups and trip purposes	Efficiency and Comfort: path connectivity continuity and directness, convenience, land use diversity, sidewalk width, pavement quality; conspicuousness and visibility of landmarks and wayfinding; public space planning and design standards; Safety and security: coexistence between pedestrian and other modes, location of pedestrian crossings and traffic, vigilance effect and perception; Attractiveness: conviviality of meeting places and anchor places, street design;	<i>O; EJ</i>	Neighbourhoods and street surveys; GIS databases	2 districts of Lisbon; neighbourhood and street level	A participatory and GIS-based walkability assessment framework (IAAPE) able to address different scales and to consider the differences between pedestrian groups and trip motives in the urban design evaluation. IAAPE i based on a set of indicators for quantifying or qualifying the accessibility and attractiveness of Pedestrian Environments	SP
Owen et al. (2007)	Public health	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: street connectivity, street intersection density, and proximity; Attractiveness: dwelling density, land-use mix, net retail area	<i>O</i>	Census data; GIS databases, survey;	Adelaide, Australia; 2650 adults recruited from 32 neighbourhood s with high or low walkability; district level	(PLACE study) Calculation of a walkability index based on the relevant environmental attributes for each district and individual measures of walking with the International Physical Activity Questionnaire-Long Form (IPAQ). Use of multilevel models to examine the associations between neighbourhood walkability attributes and walking	RB
Peiravian et al. (2014)	Urban and transport planning	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: intersection density; Attractiveness: land-use diversity, commercial density, population density	<i>O</i>	Census, GIS data	City of Chicago; sub traffic zones level	Development of a Pedestrian Environment Index	-

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Pikora et al. (2002)	Public health	Relation between built environment and physical activity	Efficiency and comfort: street permeability; intersections distance and design, walking surface, streets layout, sedibility, trees; Safety and security: lighting, surveillance; traffic volume, on street parking, crossing characteristics, path/lane obstruction, social width; Attractiveness: destinations presence; number and type of buildings; Pleasantness: Aesthetic of streetscape, sky exposure, facade continuity, softness, visual complexity architecture, trees, maintenance, pollution, cleanliness	O; EJ	Data collected with audit; information from external sources (i.e. traffic authorities); GIS datasets	Perth Western Australia; street level	Assessment of reliability of the SPACES audit instrument (Systematic Pedestrian and Cycling Environmental Scan) for collecting detailed street-level data on physical environmental factors that potentially may influence walking and cycling in local neighbourhoods	EX; SP
Porta and Renne (2005)	Urban planning	Relationship between built environment and urban sustainability	Efficiency and comfort: cost; sedibility; design of the street; Attractiveness: presence; typology; Pleasantness: softness of spaces; scenery; site's atmosphere; Safety and security: Urban texture; Presence of activities	O	Statistical data; survey data with photos	Fremantle and Joondalup, Perth, Australia; road survey; street level	Implementation of eight indicators of urban fabric and streetscape by use of photos and GIS processing. Maps of neighbourhood and street performance and cluster analysis on the photo- by-photo database	-
Rogers et al. (2010)	Urban planning	Influence on urban form on social capital and walkability;	Efficiency and comfort: frequency of walk; cost (distance, time); Pleasantness: trusting; Security: trusting	EJ	Neighbourhood audits, statistical data; demos; social capital metrics	Manchester and Portsmouth; census block	Walkability and Social Capital indicators (Capability approach and Robert Putnam's social capital theory)	-
Ruiz-Padillo et al. 2018	Transport and urban planning	Influence of urban form on physical activity	Efficiency and comfort: road connectivity; steepness of the street, sidewalk width; buildings quality (visual and aesthetic), street furniture quality and cleanliness; pavement materials Safety and security: high vehicle traffic flow, crosswalks, assaults and thefts incidence; number of shops and services typology;	O	Neighbourhood audits, statistical data; demos;	City of Porto Alegre, Brazil,	Implementation of different multi-criteria analysis methods to determine the weights of variables used in walkability measures according to citizens' preferences. Comparison of analytical techniques to verify their robustness and consistency and the coherence of results	SP
Saelens et al. (2003)	Public health	Influence of urban form on physical activity	Attractiveness: residential density; mixed land use; Efficiency and comfort: street pattern and street connectivity; land use mix-access; sidewalks and pedestrian/bike trails; Safety and security: traffic safety and crime safety; Pleasantness: aesthetics;	O; EJ	Measure of physical activity by accelerometer; survey with self-report measures of neighbourhood environment	San Diego, California; 107 adults of 2 neighbourhoods with high and low walkability; neighbourhood level	Use of Neighbourhood Environmental Walkability Scale (NEWS) and the Godin-Shephard Leisure Time Exercise Questionnaire. Intraclass correlation model to evaluate the test-retest reliability of the self-reported measures of built environment; variance and covariance analysis and regression models to investigate neighbourhood differences	RB
Schlossberg (2006)	Transport and urban planning	Relationship between urban form and pedestrian mobility	Efficiency and comfort: street network, road types (major, minor), impedance characteristics, street connectivity, intersection density; pedestrian catchment area ratio;	O	GIS dataset	Oregon; 4 middle school areas and transit stop zones; catchment area level (1.5 mi)	GIS-based qualitative visualization and quantitative analyses for the evaluation of pedestrian-oriented environments. Development of a pedestrian audit instruments with mobile GIS technology to make data gathering easier and faster	-
Su et al. 2019	Transport and urban planning	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: street connectivity; sidewalk width, slope and curvature; Attractiveness: land use mix; destination density; Pleasantness: greenspace coverage and quality Security: perceived greenery and enclosure	O	Census, demos; geodatabase; camera signaling data	Hangzhou metropolitan area, China	Development of an <i>integrated walkability index (IWI)</i> through the catastrophe theory (CT) model. Use of spatial autocorrelation analysis to examine the spatial disparities of street walkability	RB
Sundquist et al. (2011)	Urban planning and public health	Influence of urban form on physical activity; relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: street connectivity; Attractiveness: land-use mix, residential density;	O; EJ	Census, demos; geodatabase; survey;	32 Stockholm; neighbourhood level	Walkability index and statistical analysis based on multilevel linear regression model (Goldstein)	RB
Talen (2002)	Urban Planning	Relationship between physical environment and walking behaviour	Efficiency and comfort: path distance and topography; Safety: design speed of the route; design of the street; Attractiveness: presence; typology; quality	O; EJ	Census data; demos	Portland; census block	Relationship between access and spatial equity issues, quality access as a way of promoting a good urban form	-

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Van Dyck et al. (2011)	Public health	Influence of urban form on physical activity and on individual quality of life. <i>The "PLACE" theory</i>	Pleasantness: scenery; neighbourhood satisfaction; urban texture; cleanliness/pollution; architectural and urban design; landscape design; Security: crime/police presence; Attractiveness: mix of activities, typology; Comfort: noise level	<i>HS; O; EJ</i>	Questionnaire; planning data; demos	Ghent (59 neighbourhoods); 3500 Belgian adults (20-65); statistical sector	Descriptive statistics of the sample characteristics; multilevel multiple linear regression models	RB
Van Dyck et al.(2013)	Public health	Influence of urban form on physical activity	Efficiency and comfort: shelters and shade; cost; design of the street; design of the street (connectivity); signalisation; Pleasantness: scenery; architectural and urban design; cleanliness/pollution; urban texture; Safety and security: separation features; lighting; activities' atmosphere; volume/crowding if cars in the street; design of the street; crime/policy presence; urban texture; Attractiveness: residential density; mix of activities and typology;	<i>O; EJ</i>	Statistical data; telephone and mail surveys; demos, social data	Seattle, Baltimore Adelaide, Ghent; adults; administrative unit	Use of <i>Neighbourhood Environmental Walkability Scale (NEWS) and the International Physical Activity Questionnaire</i> Generalized additive mixed models (GAMMs) with negative binomial variance and logarithmic link functions NEWS-CFA scoring procedure	RB
Walkonomics	Urban and transportation planning	Influence of urban form on travel behaviour	Attractiveness: presence and number of activities; Efficiency and comfort: street width, physical barriers, provision and quality of pavement, presence of sidewalk; slope; Safety and security: lighting, vandalism, graffiti and presence of police; road accident statistics, street type, traffic speeds. Pleasantness: cleanliness, presence of trees or green vegetation, site atmosphere, aesthetic of places, architectural and landscape design, scenery, pedestrian activity;	<i>O; J</i>	Geospatial open data and crowdsourced reviews from local residents and visitor	San Francisco, New York and England streets; street level	Development of a synthetic index for each point of the map. The software gives an evaluation (5-star ratings of pedestrian friendliness) starting from available data, then all the users can rate the streets differently and refine data	SP
Walkshed	Urban and transportation planning	Influence of urban form on travel behaviour	Attractiveness: presence; Efficiency and comfort: impedance factors	<i>O</i>	City governments, Bing, and InfoUSA, and NYC Data Mine	Philadelphia and New York; street level	Development of a walkshed index	-